

Me and My Research: Exploring the Academic and Social Challenges of Researchers at Higher Education

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 02,2025</p> <p>Accepted: May 02,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Research, Challenges, Academic,Social</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15326661</p>	<p><i>Researchers faced a variety of challenges during their research work which affect their research processes and research outcomes. Consequently, researchers got demotivated and lose their interest in research. Considering this crucial issue in higher education this study aimed to explore the academic and social challenges of researchers which they faced during their research work in higher education. Qualitative research methodology was adopted to conduct this research. Convenient sampling technique was applied to collect data from fifty students studying at M. Phil and PhD programs at Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. A semi-structured interview protocol was developed to collect data from respondents. All the data were managed and analyzed manually by applying thematic analysis technique. Findings were categorized within academic and social challenges. Access to learning resources and poor academic writing, interaction with supervisors and data collect were found most dominating challenges than others. The intensity of these challenges was the same for both male and female students but with minor differences. Limitations and directions for future research was discussed.</i></p>

Introduction

The social and economic growth is mainly dependent on higher education institutes (Guerrero et al., 2016). The role of higher education is substantial to attract educated people, transfer of knowledge and to contributing in knowledge based economy (Perkmann, Tartari, McKelvey, Autio, Broström, D'este, &Sobrero, 2013). The core responsibility of higher education institutes is research because academia is one of the stakeholders to address societal problems and drive the way to boost knowledge based economy (Albatch, 2013). Research is a systematic inquiry of prevailing issues and challenges and to explore about new facts, attitudes, skills, values, or to re-evaluate the existing knowledge (Alsied& Ibrahim, 2018). The role of researcher cannot be ignored in this whole process of research. Researchers give their best in the formation of new knowledge, procedures, products, methods and systems under the supervision of their learned and professional supervisors (Creswell, Hanson, Plano, & Morales, 2007). The role of researchers is essentially based on two parts, first, they follow the principles to develop a rational about certain phenomena and their personal traits helps to conceptualize the new situations in an innovative way. Next, their personal traits also help them to build a liaison and relationship with his/her respondents (Maxwell, 2012). However, the whole process of research cannot be imagined or completed without challenges and hurdles. This could be one of the reasons that most of the students are reluctant to conduct research in their degree programs or feel pressured doing research (Sachitra, 2016). These varied nature of challenges can be divided in two parts, the academic challenges and social challenges.

Academic challenges include, selection of research problem, lack of research experience, lack of interaction with supervisors (Iqbal, Joyce, Russo, & Earnest, 2012) lack of guidance and support from supervisors (Matin& Khan, 2017; Sachitra, 2016; Duze, 2010), poor academic writing (Angu, 2013), lack of cooperation from the parent institutes, access to library resources, problems in data collection, data analysis, writing literature review and report writing etc. (Rimando et al., 2015).

In addition to academic challenges, researchers are also facing following social challenges which creates hurdles and delays in conducting their research, time management (Bocar, 2013), ethical considerations, personal and family problems (Iqbal et al., 2012), challenges in research funding and institutional support, lack of motivation (Duze, 2010), uncomfortable environment (Bocar, 2013). These challenges will be discussed in the further section of the manuscript.

Conducting research at higher education is an integral part of degree programs, however this journey is full of challenges and problems. Taking into account this serious issue this study is aimed to explore the academic and social challenges of researchers faced during their research work.

Research Objectives

Following objectives are being formulated for this study:

1. To explore the academic and social challenges faced by researchers during their theses writing.
2. To identify the academic and social challenges of male and female researchers during their theses writing.

Literature Review

Research in higher education has been receiving a great attention during the last two decades. Research is embedded in all the higher education degree programs, this enables students to gain insight and skills through systematic research processes, from collecting data to analysis and to disseminate research findings to concern stakeholders (Alsied & Ibrahim, 2018). Students' academic experience is comprising on various attributes e.g., knowledge, skills, competencies etc., researchers also considered social challenges as an important factor in conducting research. The outcome and quality of research can also have linked to these academic and social experiences (Wayt, 2012). The quality of research is usually based on the availability of academic resources and relationship between supervisors, institutional stakeholders and research respondents (Juvonen & Wentzel, 1996). The uneven cooperation among these stakeholders and unavailability of academic resources could affect the quality and process of research. We categorized these challenges in two types, academic and social challenges. The following section will present the detail of these major challenges in conducting research in higher education.

Academic Challenges

Academic challenges are mainly related to supervisors and supervisee. Furthermore, it can be related to research processes, facilities and environment, selection of a research problem, challenges in reviewing the literature, lack of support from supervisors, access to relevant literature and poor writing skills, lack of authentic data, challenges in publishing research and institutional problems etc. are considered to be as major challenges in research (ACER, 2010).

Selection of a research problem

We conduct research to address a problem in terms of highlighting the societal problems or to develop a solution of the problem. But, this all depend on the selection of the research problem. This is most important step in conducting research at any stage or degree program. Researchers consider this step a very challenging and crucial (Qasem & Zayid, 2019). Since, this is the first step in research and the whole research design is based on this step. Thus, researchers need a careful thought, support and a thorough guidance from their supervisors. It is not possible for young or inexperienced researchers to choose the research topic for themselves and develop the whole plan of research without the guidance of their supervisors. A weak and inappropriate research problem can lead the researcher to failure and could raise a number of problems in terms of data collection, research instruments and data analysis etc.

Challenges in reviewing the literature

Reviewing the related literature to conduct research is considered to be another difficult task for researchers in higher education. Review of literature requires skill and training that must be part of course work, students can practice these skills by doing their class assignments and projects. Such skills ultimately facilitate them in conducting research. There is a big pool of data on internet, it is sometime difficult to find the relevant and latest data. A lack of skills and training could make this more difficult for researchers to find the relevant and required data (Moosavi, 2020). Teachers should train their students to find the quality data, sometimes, quality literature cannot be accessed due to subscriptions charges and an institute are not able to subscribe with such websites or journals so it creates problems for researchers. However, supervisors can facilitate their researchers by using their professional contacts in the related filed or by creating networking with such organizations and institutes (Haddaway, et al., 2020). The detail of these resources will be discussed in the following section.

Access to learning resources

In spite of increasing and widening development in Open Educational Resources and access to high quality learning resources yet there are challenges for researchers to access the required data (Coughlan & Perryman, 2011). In fact, access to learning resources is a major challenge for researchers in developing countries. Universities and institutes for higher education could not afford to take subscriptions of top journals. Ultimately, library resources are limited to showcase the latest journals, books and other learning resources (Annuobi, 2009). In the modern era, everything is being linked with internet and technology, in case of libraries, huge amount of funds are being allocated to facilitate students in conducting their research projects (Mahwasane & Mudzielwana, 2016). But, the available funds for higher education are not sufficient to fulfill the need. Due to lack of resources researcher left with no option to depend on low quality data which again affecting the quality of their own work. Moreover, our students and researchers are not well trained to use such resources in their academics and research and they usually depend on unauthentic sources. Okello-Obura and Magara (2008) conducted their research in a developing country and identified the same that lack of technological training made them incapable of accessing online resources.

Poor academic writing

Academic writing holds an utmost importance in research work and in report writing (Carlino, 2012).

The success in research is mainly depend on the research skills of the researcher and later the practical use of these skills turn into dissertation (Castelló, Iñesta, &Corcelles, 2013). Publishing research is also linked to your skills in writing, even experienced and skilled researchers sometimes struggle to publish their research (Emerson, 2012; Swales & Feak, 2004). This scenario is different in developing countries, where universities do not emphasize on research skills and academic writing. Resultantly, poor academic writing led them to failure in research (Fareed & Ashraf, 2016; Manchishi, Ndhlovu and Mwanza, 2015). Such students cannot present their findings properly, they failed to follow the standard format of writing and unable to write the literature. The role of supervisor is very crucial in this regard to teach such skills to their researchers and give them proper and productive feedback to improve their work. Moreover, poor academic writing in developing countries could also be due to English as a second language. Due to their language skills, such students are struggling with writing (Yiu , 2009).

In Pakistani context, researchers in higher education are struggling with academic writing and this can be due to their level of competency in English language, lack of ideas, and exposure with the language (Fareed & Ashraf, 2016). It is hard for them to transfer their ideas on papers and report the findings in a scientific way (Haider, 2012). The competency in research requires strong writing skills, critical and analyzing skills but poor writing skills will leave researchers with trouble and failure (Ahleet & Rumman, 2019).

Institutional problems

Institution plays an important role in setting up a research environment. If institutional policy is not supportive for research they will not pay attention to research initiatives and facilities. All types of research facilitation in terms of labs, instruments, data collection, funding etc. come through institutions (Castelló, Iñesta, &Corcelles, 2013). Funding for research and related tasks is also very important, non-availability of funding can affect the research process, output of research and disseminating the research. Next to institutions, supervisors' role is of great importance in conducting research work. However, supervisors' support and initiatives are also based on intuitional policy and facilities. Supervisor is the only person who can create a research environment for his/her students and can facilitate them in their research work without their support and cooperation researchers cannot work productively (Griffiths, Blakey, & Vardy, 2016).

Social Challenges

In addition to academic challenges, social challenges could also affect the research process and its outcomes. During the research process a researcher can face a variety of social problems which could hinder his/her research process in view of data collection, research instruments, analysis, report writing and most important ethical issues (Manchishi, Ndhlovu, & Mwanza, 2015). There could be a number of challenges but certain challenges are being discussed below:

Relationship between supervisor and supervisee

The relationship between supervisor and supervisee is the most important part in research. A healthy, supportive and cooperative relationship is essential in research process (Akyürek & Afacan, 2018). A supportive and cooperative relationship could shape up an excellent research proposal and dissertation as well, but in contrast, if the relationship between these two major stakeholders is not supportive enough it can create problems for both of them and hinder the research process (Moosavi, 2020).

Similarly, frequent interaction with supervisor facilitate researchers in research, if this interaction is not on regular basis, researchers can face serious problems. It is often observed that supervisors do not give sufficient time to their researchers and put them on waiting, they also took a lot of time to give them feedback. Researchers need timely guidance and support from their supervisors, such behaviors of supervisors affect the motivation and satisfaction of researchers towards their work and could also affect the output of research. In fact, research is already a stressful task for students, if they face such issues and lose their motivation and interest how they can do a productive research (Qasem & Zayid, 2019). This challenge is also on the part of researchers as well, many students who are doing their higher degrees also doing parallel jobs. Research is a kind of part time activity for them and they do not have any pressure from the institute and they have irregular interaction with their supervisors which ultimately affect the quality of work and cause delays in submissions (Kasworm, 2009).

Challenges in data collection

Data collection is the most challenging task in research process, at this step you are dependent on others. Sometime respondents are not approachable and sometimes they are reluctant to participate in research, this cause delay in data collection (Moosavi, 2020). In the same way, sometimes researchers need to access official documents for data collection. For this purpose, they need to get official approvals from authorities which take a lot of time and sometime results of such efforts are useless. Such organizations never facilitate researcher without institutional support and reference. On the other end, institution and supervisor hardly cooperate with researchers to facilitate them in data collection.

Time management

As mentioned elsewhere, researchers do not manage their time efficiently, they are usually engaged in jobs and could not spare sufficient time for their research (Qasem & Zayid, 2019). In Pakistani context, the doctoral

students do not manage their time properly and unable to meet their study goals. In this way they look for shortcuts and try to complete their work in rush which affect the quality of their work. In contrast, the best practice organizations develop sound programs to engage their students in productive work and set goals for each term or year (Akyürek & Afacan, 2018).

Financial challenges

Finances is the utmost factor in research work, both researchers and supervisors needs finances to conduct research. Institutions should allocate sufficient amount for research, lab work, instruments, data collection, data analyses and publications. There are major funding cuts on higher education in developed and developing countries which is affecting higher education around the world (Mitchell, Leachman, & Masterson, 2017). There comes the role of donor agencies, many agencies are providing funds to higher education to conduct research on certain pre-defined areas. Universities should try to align their goals with them to get some funding from these donor agencies (Tandberg, & Anderson, 2020). Universities should also facilitate their students in research work through their own resources.

Personal problems

Next to all these above mentioned challenges in research, researchers also have some personal problems during their research work. These problems related to finances, social backgrounds, students who are living in far flung areas faced difficulties in conducting research, transportation problems, family problems, some students cannot handle stress, time management and lack of skills in using technology etc. These problems appear to researchers as major problems in conducting research. Above all stress is found more difficult to handle by researchers (Christian, Johnstone, Larkins, Wright, & Doran, 2021).

Method

This study intended to investigate the academic and social challenges of researchers faced during their research work in higher education.

Procedure

The present study was conducted to identify the academic and social challenges of researchers encountered during these writing. A qualitative research methodology was applied to collect data from the researchers of M. Phil and PhD programs. A semi-structured interview protocol was designed to collect data from the selected participants. All the data were managed manually for analysis purpose. Considering the nature of data, thematic analysis found to be a best suited technique to infer certain findings.

Sampling

The sample of study was consisted on M. Phil and PhD students enrolled in various sessions from 2014 to 2019 in M. Phil and PhD programs at Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan. These students were enrolled in various faculties and departments, including sciences, social sciences, engineering, pharmacy, agriculture and computer sciences etc. Respondents were selected on convenient basis from all the above mentioned disciplines to present a clear and bigger picture of the phenomenon under study. In total 50 researchers (Females=22) and (Males=28) were involved in this qualitative research.

Measures

In depth literature was reviewed to scrutinize the academic and social challenges highlighted by different researchers in various contexts. This helps to design the semi-structured interview protocol. In total ten questions were formulated with some supporting questions. The supporting questions facilitated in inquiring the details of their varied research experiences and challenges which they were facing at different stages of research. The first question was started with the introduction of the participants and after asking some general question researcher moved towards specific questions. Following are the sample questions: (i) *What do you think; how far academic writing is a major challenge for researchers?* (ii) *What was the usual behavior/response of people when you visit them for data collection?*

Data collection

All the respondents were contacted through their faculties and departments. Researcher visited the departments to collect the details of their students involved in M. Phil and PhD programs. After obtaining the consent from Deans and Head, researcher get the data and contacted the students to obtain their consent to participate in this research. Individual meetings were set up with those students who showed their willingness to participate in research. Some of the participants were on jobs so they were interviewed through phone calls. Prior to the interview, researcher shared the objectives of the research and present them with the interview protocol to give them an idea about questions. All the interviews were recorded verbatim for analysis.

All the ethical guidelines were ensured in view of data management and data reporting.

Pseudo names were used to report the results of the study. As to ensuring the reliability of the coding scheme, an independent coder was hired to code eight interviews, later coding was compared with the researcher to develop the agreement. The inter-rater reliability was found 93% which is in line with the standards of Miles, & Huberman (1994). Each interview was lasted between 20 to 30 minutes.

Data analysis

As mentioned above, thematic analysis was carried out to analyze the collected data. First, all the data were transcribed verbatim. To get familiar with data, all the transcripts were read carefully and organized in a logical manner, coding scheme was designed according to the research objectives and interview questions. After designing the codes list, certain themes were designed. At next steps, all the themes were reviewed carefully, some of the themes renamed and drafted properly, and lastly, similar themes were merged together.

Results and Discussion

The main objective of this study was to explore the academic and social challenges of research which they faced during their research work. The thematic analysis helped us to identified the five main themes under each category 'academic' and 'social' challenges.

At first we will present and discuss the findings of academic challenges with the help of interview occurrences.

Academic Challenges

Selection of a research problem

Selection of the research problem was highlighted by some of the respondents, females faced it more challenging as compare to male students. Students found this step very challenging due to lack of skills and knowledge in the selection of a research problem. Students invested a lot of time to select a research problem. Our findings are in line with the study finding of Alsied and Ibrahim (2017) they explore that students faced problems at the time of topic selection and this consumed a lot of time. Following respondents highlighted this challenge:

One of the respondents said:

"I have consumed a lot of time in topic selection for my research. Due to this time waste, it was very difficult to complete the work on time. But, I fee, If I would have been guided properly, I could have save my time." (RP-04)

Another respondent shared:

"Topic selection was such a difficult task for me, I could not understand from where to start, what to study, what area I should focus on.....(...). Thus, it was a very disappointing time of my research work." (RP-16)

Challenges in reviewing the literature

Literature review considered to be another challenge for researchers. Again, this step of research proved to be more difficult and challenging for female students as compare to male students. Writing literature review is usually a critical task which required skills, training and guidance. Earlier research also concluded this fact, the study of Qasem, (2019) and Alsied, (2017) explored the same that researchers faced serious challenges in view of writing literature review. Respondents mentioned the following in their interviews:

One of the respondents shared:

"We have advised to read articles, I have read a lot but unfortunately I do not have the require and proper training to develop the literature. My supervisor never guided me on developing literature review." (RP-40)

Another stated:

"It was very difficult for me to write the literature review, usually I copy the literature from the available sources but after knowing the plagiarism policy, I was in trouble in developing literature. We discussed with our supervisors and later he started guiding us about writing and literature development." (RP-29)

Access to learning resources

Access to learning resources was identified as a major challenge by researchers, female students found it more difficult in contrast to male students. Students are not properly trained and taught to access learning resources. This create serious problem when writing their dissertation. Existing research conducted in Pakistani context and other contexts identified the same findings in their studies (Ali, 2018; Rajasekar, 2013). Research respondents explained this challenge in a following way:

One of the researchers said:

"Access to learning resources is extremely challenging task in research process. Access to such sources is very expensive and only institutions and higher education could arrange this success for their students. But unfortunately, this is quite a neglected area in higher education or may be not a priority for the institutes. Lack of such resources resulted in low quality work." (RP-04)

Another respondent highlighted:

"Most of the online resources are paid and locked due to access issues. We are deprived to access these resources; this affect the quality of our work." (RP-05)

Poor academic writing

Poor academic writing skills identified as the second highest challenge for researchers. They rated academic writing as a complex and difficult task and they were never trained to practice this. Interestingly, both male and female researchers found this a difficult task. Following interview occurrences is the evidence of their difficulties. Our study findings are also in accordance with the study findings of Bitchener and Basturkmen (2006); Al-Khairy (2013), they have identified that poor academic writing skills are the major challenge for the researchers in higher education.

A respondent stated:

“For me understanding and compliance with the rules of American Psychological Association (APA) was highly difficult. We were never practiced such things and it was so difficult to take care the APA rules while writing.” (RP-04)

One more researcher explained in the following way:

“We were working on difference assignments and mostly we depend on copied material we never know the writing rules. When it comes to thesis writing and taking care the plagiarism while writing, it is becoming very difficult.” (RP-41)

Another participant stated:

“Academic writing required expertise in language. Since, English is not our first language, we usually write in a way as we speak. Academic writing is based on certain rules and techniques which can be learned through practice and guidance. For example, paraphrasing was very challenging for me and no one helped me to guide on it.”

Institutional problems

The majority of the students are facing problems in their research due to institutional policies and facilities. During interviews researchers highlighted various types of challenges in view of their experiences which they faced during their research work. Surprisingly, male students highlighted these challenges more as compare to their counterparts. Available research conducted by Bocar (2013) explored the similar results that lack of cooperation from the institutes created many problems for researchers which in line with our findings. Respondents claimed the lack of intuitional support and cooperation. Respondents reported these challenges in a following way:

One of the participants said:

“What I have suffered more during my work was the unavailability of data analysis software. University does not facilitate its students in data analysis, data management and analysis. We need certain software but the software are highly expensive and we as students could not afford to buy. The pirated versions of these software do not offer complete functions of the software.” (RP-37)

Another researcher stated:

“Being a science student, we need fully functional labs, related materials and instruments. Lack of such things create delays in experiments and results. Moreover, due to number of students, we could not get sufficient time to work in labs. This ultimately slow down our research process.” (RP-24)

Another respondent said:

“Our department has no proper policy to choose supervisors, there is a list of supervisors but how we can select a supervisor without knowing their expertise or preferences in research. This create frustration and cause delay as well.” (RP-27)

Social Challenges

As to social challenges, following themes were highlighted during data analysis.

Interaction between supervisor and supervisee

Lack of interaction between supervisor and supervisee was identified as one of the key challenges during data analysis. Both male and female researchers reported their irregular meetings with their respective supervisors. They claimed delay in response, lack of guidance and support from their supervisors. Earlier research conducted in Asian contexts concluded the same results that lack of interaction between supervisors and supervisee could create serious challenges for researchers (Yousefi et al., 2015; Ismail, 2011). Following interview quotes support this claimed:

A research participant stated:

“My supervisor was an extremely busy person, he remained busy in multiple meetings and projects. I was doing job at that time and took off from my job to see my supervisor. In spite of appointment with him, he kept me waiting for the whole day. I use to send my work via email but he took a long time to respond.” (RP-04)

A respondent explained:

“I had a tough time during my research work, my supervisor does not give me proper time, she suggested to take help from other teachers or advised me to complete the work by my own. I always missed her support in my work.” (RP-25)

Another said:

“I had faced a lot of difficulties during my research work. My supervisor always put pressure on me. For example, in case of budget, there are a lot of conditions using budget which means you are not allowed to do anything. If we work in a lab, we are always conveyed very harshly to use experimental kits carefully otherwise you are responsible. This kind of attitude put pressure on students and they cannot work productively. I lost my interest in research due to this behavior.” (RP-01)

Challenges in data collection

Challenges in data collection was reported as most difficult part in research which is highlighted by all the respondents. They highlighted their difficulties and experiences in data collections. Both male and female students experienced the same level of difficulties in their data collection. Both Rimando (2012) and Dearnley (2005) conducted their studies to identify the challenges of researchers and concluded with the fact that it is the most reported challenge in their studies which is in line with our study results. Researchers faced variety of challenges in data collection which is usually unavoidable. One of the respondents shared the following:

Research participant reported:

“What I have experienced during data collection, respondents were not serious in giving their true responses. They were not take it serious and fill my questionnaire without any interest. Some of the respondents were making fun of my questionnaire. Such attitudes not only affected the research process but research findings as well.” (RP-03)

Another reported:

“My respondents were very unique in view of their disease, so I have to visit psychiatrist, general physician, dietitians to find such patients. It was a very hard experience. Sometime, respondents were reluctant to share their health details with researcher.” (RP-47)

One of respondents said:

“I have conducted an intervention which was based on a training, it was very difficult for me to handle all the respondents. Since, they were students so it was very difficult to handle them. There was no support from my supervisors and department to conduct this training.” (RP-38)

Another participant said:

“I have involved police personnel in my research, it was extremely difficult to schedule meetings with them to collect data. I sent the questionnaire via email but it took me a long time to receive their responses.” (RP-03)

Challenges in time management

Time management was also identified as a big challenge by researchers. In fact, they were not properly trained to conduct their research work. For example, after spending a lot of time in topic selection, researchers get panic to complete their work on time. Sometime, there were summer vacations or semester break which again affect their working schedule. Sometime, they were keep on waiting to meet their supervisor or to receive their feedback which waste their time. Both male and female students complain about this mismanagement and consider it a major challenge during research work. Ali (2018); Dombeck and Wells-Moran (2006) identified time management as most highlighted challenge by the researchers. Researchers could not manage their time efficiently which affect their research goals and output which is aligned with our findings. Their shared their experience in a following way:

As stated by one of the respondents:

“The nature of my research was a bit different than other students, I had involved working and house wives and their children in my research. It took a long time to get their consent and data from them. So, at the end, much of my time was invested in data collection and I could not achieve my other goals to complete my work on time.” (RP-46)

Another research participant expressed:

“I was on job during my research work, it was very difficult me for me to manage the data collection with my job. So, in this way, I could not complete my work on time.” (RP-30)

Financial challenges

Financial challenges also highlighted by both male and female researchers. But male students faced this challenges more as compare to female students. Lack of financial assistance and resources affect students' research work, this finding is completely in line with the study findings of Taskeen et al., (2014) who identified that researcher face financial issue at each step of their research starting from data collection to publishing their work.

A research participant reported:

"Financial problems are beyond our control. We have to pay heavy fees for M. Phil and PhD degrees and then to manage funds for research work. You require funds at each stage of your research." (RP-27)

One more respondent expressed:

"In science subjects, there are limited resources in labs, sometimes you need to pay by yourself to get your experiments done. Similarly, if you want to publish your research you again need funds. I think, research cannot be completed without proper funds." (RP-27)

Personal and family problems

Personal and family problems are another major challenge revealed by researchers. Surprisingly, male researchers faced more personal and family problems as compare to female researchers. The research findings of Bocar (2013) and Duze (2010) also corroborate with our findings that personal and domestic problems can distract the attention of researchers which ultimately affect their research outcomes.

One researcher expressed this in the following way:

"I was doing a job during my degree, so it was quite difficult to manage my research work and job at the same time. And ultimately, both my work and job affected." (RP-39)

Another participant stated:

"Next to research work, I was also doing a job and managing my family. It was a hard time of my life. I could not give proper time to my research. At the end both my family and work suffered and the quality of my work was also got affected." (RP-45)

Another researcher said:

"Being an older member of my family, I have a lot many domestic responsibilities. I am an earning hand for my family. I could not manage time for my research. I know it is my personal problem. But, I really feel, my research is getting affected." (RP-08)

Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

The study aimed to investigate the academic and social challenges of researchers which they faced during their research work. We tried to stretch the scope of our research within a university to include the opinion from variety of departments and researchers yet there are certain limitations which need to stress and can be considered in future researchers. As to sample, we have sampled students from one public sector university which can be expanded to further universities in future researchers. There are chances that this university is being faced certain challenges due to funds, developing institution policy for research and lacking in required resources. Secondly, we have only involved students in this research, future research can involve supervisor as well to know their stance on these challenges or might be they have some other challenges in view of conducting research in their respective faculties and departments. Moreover, we have mainly conducted thematic analysis and dependent on interview quotes to report the findings. Next to qualitative findings, researchers can also quantify the findings for better presentation of the results.

Conclusion

The study aimed to explore the academic and social challenges of researchers which they faced during their research work in higher education. We have categorized these challenges as academic and social. As to academic challenges we merge and limit these challenges in five aspects; *selection of a research problem, challenges in reviewing the literature, access to learning resources, poor academic writing and institutional problems*. Although, researchers highlighted all these aspects very challenging but access to learning resources and poor academic writing was considered as the most serious challenges for researchers. Both male and female researchers are facing these challenges in the same manners.

As to social challenges, we have identified the following key challenges, *interaction between supervisor and supervisee, challenges in data collection, challenges in time management, financial challenges and personal and family problems*. Although, researchers stressed all these challenges but interaction with supervisors, their support and cooperation were considered as the most dominating challenge. Similarly, respondents also emphasized 'data collection' as a second highest challenge during their research work.

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